

Skill Development: A Drive for Strategic Business Growth

Chandrika Prasad Das*

ABSTRACT

Globalization, modernization and development in business era have intensified the need for skill development as it will help not only in conducting business activities but also in the most effective and efficient manner. Skill is the ability and capability acquired through deliberate, systematic and sustained effort to smoothly carryout complex activities. The present paper throws light on the importance of skill in business education. It attempts to discuss various skill development programs in business education. It also focuses on the present scenario including government initiatives taken for developing skill. The study found that despite of serious attempts by government, there exist certain unresolved challenges, which need immediate attention of both government and private players. Hence, various initiatives of government should focus on these obstacles and develop programs accordingly to achieve the objective of skill development in business education completely.

Keywords: Globalization, Competitive Workforce, Skill Development, Business Education.

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge for doing a work is not enough to complete a task rather the technique is important for efficient and effective accomplishment. This technique is something related to skill. Though knowledge and skill both are required in every field, we have been focusing on knowledge since long where by skill aspect is being ignored somehow. But now the time has come to realize the importance of skill and focus on its development whether in the field of employment, personal development, and education including business education.

Skill development in business education has become vital for successful conduct of business activities which has a direct impact on the overall development of a nation.

OBJECTIVES

The followings are the objectives of this study.

1. To analyze the importance of skill development in the field of business education
2. To discuss the method of developing skill focusing on the role of government and private players
3. To find out the challenges in the process of skill development in business education and suggest various majors to overcome these.

MEANING OF SKILL DEVELOPMENT IN BUSINESS EDUCATION

Skills and knowledge are the key factors for the economic growth and social development of any country. These are the forces which enhance the competitiveness and knowhow among the workforce. Countries having higher level of skilled workforce are able to face the dynamic challenges and also can grab the opportunities. In India the maximum workforce are among 15-59 age group. So it is very important to provide them proper training and improve the skills and practical knowledge which will help them in developing their efficiency & productivity. The skilled workforce can be an important pillar for the economic growth of the nation.

Business education is a term that encompasses a number of methods used to teach students the fundamentals of business practices. These methods help them to handle business activities and day to day problems of any business. This type of education programmes are ranging from formal educational degree programs, such as the Master of Business Administration (MBA), to school-to-work opportunity systems or cooperative education. Business education programs are designed to provide students with the basic theories of management and production. The main goals

*Lecturer, B.B. Mahavidyalaya, Jajpur, Odisha, India

of business education programs are to teach the processes of decision making; the philosophy, theory, and psychology of management; practical applications; and business start-up and operational procedures.

IMPORTANCE

1. Skill development in Business Education provides several disciplines, enables people to think, behave in ways that to support the growth, efficiency and effectiveness of an organization.
2. It teaches individuals about traditional and current types of business methods and management techniques.
3. It also helpful to understand what business methods are successful and why others fail.
4. It can also alert individuals to upcoming changes in the business environment.
5. It helps in economy growth and social development in any country.
6. It helps in demonstrating inter-personal, teamwork, and leadership skill necessary to functions in multi cultural business settings.
7. It helps in selecting and applying tools and techniques for business decision making.

TYPES OF BUSINESS EDUCATION PROGRAMS

Traditional academic programs for business education include college courses that teach students the fundamentals of management, marketing, business ethics, accounting, and other relevant topics. These have been supplemented in recent years with extensive course offerings in computer skills, e-commerce management, and other factors in managing a business within the global economy. Students can earn degrees ranging from an Associate degree in business to a Ph.D (Doctor of Philosophy) in business administration. Some programs may consist of class work only, while others-such as tech-prep and cooperative education programs, internships, and school-to work opportunities-combine academics with on-the-job training.

Tech-Prep Programs

It is a skill development programme offered in cooperation between UAF community and technical college and other educational institutions allowing vocational or technical education to students to earn credit towards certificate or a degree. A tech-prep program is a four-year planned sequence of study for a technical field which students begin in their junior year of high school. The program extends through either two years of college in occupational education, or a minimum two-year apprenticeship. This programme provides students the opportunity to receive University credit for specific high school classes at a minimum cost.

Co-ops

Cooperative education (co-op) is a program which offers students a combination of college courses and work experience related to their majors. Co-op programs are available in a wide range of business disciplines, e.g., information systems, accounting, and sales. Participants enroll in a post secondary educational program while employed in a related job. Most co-op participants are paid by their employers. The co-op program provides students with the work experience they need to obtain full-time employment after graduation. More than 1,000 postsecondary educational institutions and 50,000 employers participate in co-op programs throughout the United States.

Internships

Internships are related closely to co-op programs. Interns may be school or college students or post graduate adults. These positions may be paid or unpaid. The main difference, however, is that those who participate in internship programs are not paid, as internships are designed specifically to provide participants with work experience. Often, interns will complete the program separately from their academic setting, rather than combining the two. This can be a significant benefit to employer as experienced interns often need little or no training. But the problem is that there is no guarantee a intern will get a job.

School-to-Work Programs

This programme mainly refers to on-the-job training, Apprenticeship which are designed to prepare students to

enter the job market. School-to-work opportunity programs focus on career awareness for students. They provide participants with work mastery certificates and furnish them with links to technical colleges. In these programs, all participants have jobs, apprenticeships, or further schooling after finishing high school.

Career Academies

Career academies are occupationally focused high schools that contain "schools within schools." Primarily, they train high school juniors and seniors in such areas as environmental technology, applied electrical science, horticulture, and engineering. In addition to these schools, there are also privately operated business schools that grant certificates to students who complete their programs.

All of these types of business education programs provide participants with career paths for high-skill technical and professional occupations by formally linking secondary and post-secondary education, and by integrating academic and occupational learning. Students who complete such programs gain an advantage over people who concentrate solely on the academic part of business education.

PRESENT SCENARIO UNDER GOVERNMENT INITIATIVES

This year Government has taken many Initiatives by establishing different policies which are aimed at empowering individuals through providing skills and technical knowledge. These programmes will enhance the employability and ensure an Inclusive growth. Some of the step taken by the Government to developing the skills of Indian workforce are as follows:

1. Skill India Programme

After "Digital India" and 'Make in India', the NaMo Government is to launch yet another programme. This one is a revised version of programmes launched earlier under the skill development policy. This new programme, called 'Skill India', is supposed to be a multi-skill programme. It will be launched in March 2015. Like all other programmes, 'Skill India' too is a dream project of Narendra Modi and the work to launch this programme has already been initiated.

Objectives of 'Skill India'

The main goal is to create opportunities, space and scope for the development of the talents of the Indian youth and to develop more of those sectors which have already been put under skill development for the last so many years and also to identify new sectors for skill development. The new programme aims at providing training and skill development to 500 million youth of our country by 2020, covering each and every village. Various schemes are also proposed to achieve this objective.

Features of 'Skill India'

1. The emphasis is to skill the youths in such a way so that they get employment and also improve entrepreneurship.
2. Provides training, support and guidance for all occupations that were of traditional type like carpenters, cobblers, welders, blacksmiths, masons, nurses, tailors, weavers etc.
3. More emphasis will be given on new areas like real estate, construction, transportation, textile, gem industry, jeweler designing, banking, tourism and various other sectors, where skill development is inadequate or nil.
4. The training programmes would be on the lines of international level so that the youths of our country can not only meet the domestic demands but also of other countries like the US, Japan, China, Germany, Russia and those in the West Asia.
5. Another remarkable feature of the 'Skill India' programme would be to create a hallmark called 'Rural India Skill', so as to standardize and certify the training process.
6. Tailor-made, need-based programmes would be initiated for specific age groups which can be like language and communication skills, life and positive thinking skills, personality development skills, management skills,

- behavioural skills, including job and employability skills.
7. The course methodology of 'Skill India' would be innovative, which would include games, group discussions, brainstorming sessions, practical experiences, case studies etc.

2. National Skill Development Policy

The National Skill Development Policy is aimed at empowering all individuals through improved skills, knowledge and internationally recognized qualifications to enable them to access decent employment, to promote inclusive national growth and to ensure India's competitiveness in the global market with the following aims.

1. Enhancing individual's employability and ability to adapt to changing technologies and labour market demands.
2. Strengthening competitiveness of the country.
3. Attracting investment in skill development.

OBJECTIVES

1. Create opportunities for all to acquire skills throughout life, and especially for youth, women and disadvantaged groups.
2. Promote commitment by all stakeholders.
3. Develop a high-quality skilled entrepreneur.
4. Enable the establishment of flexible delivery mechanisms.
5. Enable effective coordination between different ministries, the centre and the states and public and private providers.

3. Modular Employable Skills (MES) Scheme

The Modular Employable Skills (MES) scheme is being offered under the Skill Development Initiative Scheme (SDIS). The Ministry of Labour and Employment undertook the development of a new strategic framework, namely the MES, for skill development for early school leavers and existing workers, especially in the unorganized sector in close consultation with industry, micro enterprises in the unorganized sector, State Governments, experts and academia. The main objective of the scheme is to provide employable skills to school leavers, existing workers, ITI/ITC graduates, etc. Skill levels of persons already employed can also be tested and certified under this scheme, i.e., certification of prior/experiential learning. Public Private Partnership (PPP) envisaged in the form of active participation of the industry/private sector in every stage of design and implementation of the scheme. The MES concept has the potential to go a long way in furthering skill development as it has provided a pathway for multiple entry and exits as well as transforming skill development from long term skill acquisition periods (1 to 2 years) to short term (about 3 months).

4. National Skill Development Corporation

The National Skill Development Corporation (NSDC) is a one of its kind, Public Private Partnership in India. It aims to promote skill development by catalyzing creation of large, quality, for-profit vocational institutions. It provides viability gap funding to build scalable, for-profit vocational training initiatives. Its mandate is also to enable support systems such as quality assurance, information systems and train the trainer academies either directly or through partnerships. Its objective is to contribute significantly (about 30%) to the overall target of skilling/up skilling 500 million people in India by 2022, mainly by fostering private sector initiatives in skill development programmes and providing viability gap funding. NSDC is a not-for-profit company set up by the Ministry of Finance, under Section-25 of the Companies Act. It has an equity base of Rs. 10 crore, of which the Government of India accounts for 49%, while the private sector has the balance 51%. Other key Skill Development Initiatives of the Government are as follows:

1. Establishment of 1,500 new ITIs through the DGET
2. Establishment of 50,000 Skill Development Centers through the DGET
3. Setting up of PM National Council on Skill Development (already operational)

4. Setting up of National Skill Development Coordination Board (already operational).

ROLE OF PRIVATE SECTOR

1. Skill development through Formal, private skills education and training institutions.
2. Internship training in private enterprises
3. non-formal sector skills development
4. Private sector associations training programmes

CHALLENGES

1. Lack of co-ordination between government and institutions: Government and institutions do not co-ordinate with each other for successful completion of skill development programs at various educational institutions. Only formulation of policies is not enough. Successful execution is also equally important to achieve the purpose for which co-ordination is a must between government and institutions.
2. Shortage of fund: Fund is the most important aspect for carrying out any plan, policy. Monetary aspect can't be ignored as we talk of skill development. Shortage of fund for carrying out skill development program is the most important obstacle.
3. Private sector participation: Private players also have an important role in the field of skill development in business education. Most of the business schools are run and managed by private parties. They shouldn't only focus on earning profit rather should try for proper development of skill among students.
4. Placement linked challenge: The ultimate aim of developing skill in business education is to make students employable. So proper placement facilities must be provided after skill development programs. But now it has become difficult to provide 100% placement guarantee even after skill development training which is one of the major drawbacks. Focus should be on employability rather than only on improvement of skill.
5. Demand and supply mismatch: Demand made by industries and supply of labour force mismatch leads to aggravate all types of skill development initiatives of government and its partner agencies as:
 - a. The number of people formally trained a year is only 1, 10,000 by ministry of labour and employment and approximately 3, 20,000 by 17 other central government ministries.
 - b. In India 67% of employers find it difficult to fill jobs.
6. Infrastructure challenge: Infrastructure is the most important aspect for carrying out any developmental program. For the purpose of skill development in business education, there must be proper infrastructural facilities. But this facility is not available sufficiently which is another challenge for skill development.
7. Faculty: Efficient and eligible faculties are the pre requisites for carrying out skill development programs. But there is a lack of efficient faculties which poses a challenge for skill development in business education.
8. Third party evaluation and certification: There can be a system for third party evaluation and certification after the skill development training. But the evaluation and certification must be fair one. An unfair certification obtained can be a major obstacle in the way of skill development.

SUGGESTIONS

1. Co-ordination between government and institutions: There must be proper co-ordination between government and institutions to achieve the objective of skill development in business education. Government should formulate proper policies and institutions should carry out these policies in a right manner to achieve the objective of developing skill.
2. Policy development: Ensuring a coordinated approach across a spectrum of intervention to link government, business institutes can be possible only through proper formulation of policies. Government should focus on this by creating committees consisting efficient members.
3. Raising awareness: Awareness for need of skill development in business education must be raised through seminars, workshops which can contribute a lot towards achieving the objective.
4. Private investment: Attempt and investment only by government isn't enough for developing skill in business education. Support from private parties is also vital for easy achievement of goal. Investment from private parties must be channelized towards skill development programs.